

MICRO-MECHANICS THEORY APPLIED IN AERONAUTICAL PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT.

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1 Introduction

Criteria of strength, stiffness, fatigue and damage tolerance criteria are necessary to the composites design of the airplanes. For the strength criteria, the first ply failure (FPF) is extensively used.

In Hinton, Kaddour and Soden [1] are showed failure criteria comparing with the experimental results. The results showed the difficulty to have an unique criteria that agree with all experimental results. A new criteria is being proposed in Stephen W. Tsai [2] based in the micro-mechanics theory. In this new approach the information about failure in the fiber, resin and interfaces can be obtained. Temperature, humidity, load frequency and stress ratio considered in this criteria are useful for composites design and analysis. Therefore the main purpose of this paper is to describe two applications that were made in the EMBRAER airplanes development program, considering this theory. It should be pointed out that the results of this tool were used to give directives to the certification campaign. The test results, confirmed the expectations.

2 Certification Challenge Definitions

2.1 Environmental Load Factor (ELF)

There are many challenges and issues in the aeronautics certification. When the subject is composites structure, the ELF is one that is uncertain to obtain. ELF is a factor that employer prefers to use in the room temperature test condition (figure 1) instead to test the component inside an ambient with temperature and humidity controlled, figure 2. In this case, the test load is increased by ELF. $ELF = 1.00$ means that the component is being tested exactly in the real critical condition. Another factor that influences the weight of the component is the

Load Enhancement Factor (LEF) as described in the MIL-HDBK-17 [3] and [4]. In the Phenom 100, EMBRAER airplane, the empennage test was overloaded with ELF and LEF.

2.2 Spectrum Loading Reduction

One issue that affects the cost of the certification is the test time duration. In the certification is necessary to show residual strength in the ultimate load after fatigue cycles of the airplane [5], [6]. Therefore the challenge in this case is to decide about the truncation [3, 10] and/or reduction of the spectrum loading in the fatigue test without affect the original condition. The figure 3, shows one interpretation of the truncation proposed in the cited references. This decision affects the test duration and consequently the cost of the certification. One suggestion about spectrum truncation is the rule stated in the MIL-HDBK-17 and that is reproduced here: “*Although there are no general guidelines for spectrum truncation for composite fatigue tests, the fatigue threshold of the material is usually used to determine the cycles to be truncated. Stress (strain) levels below the fatigue threshold are considered to cause no fatigue damage (initiation or progression) and theoretically can be removed from the spectrum without changing the test results. However, in practice, the truncation level is usually a certain percentage of the A- or B-basis fatigue threshold (e.g. 60% to 70%)*”. In the Phenom 300, EMBRAER airplane, the composites flap test was the critical way to the certification. That is, the test duration considering the original spectrum loading would affect the deadline of the certification campaign. So, the reduction and/or truncation in the original fatigue spectrum would be necessary to do. Then, using the tool [8], a simulation was performed to decide about the proposal test which goal was

spectrum loading reduction to comply with the certification campaign established.

3 Results

3.1 ELF Application

The knowing of the ELF in the begin of the certification campaign is important to give information to the test set-up design. There are many discussion about how ELF can be obtained. The modes of failure indicates the criteria to obtain the ELF. And as mentioned there are many failure criteria to take into account. In the other hand, the composites durability data is very difficult to obtain. Therefore using the Super Mic-Mac (SMM) tool, the simulation results is quickly obtained. The figures 4 and 5 shows the results for two simulations, considering two different temperature. Observe that in this case, ELF is very sensitive with the differences of the temperature. Considering this simulation, one quantity of the specimens were made to determine one ELF approach. The report of the reference [7] confirmed the expectation about the ELF simulation.

3.2 Spectrum Loading Reduction Application

Extensive study in original spectrum loading is made to decide a possible reduction in the spectrum with the same results prior. Usually the transfer function, that is, transformation of the load spectrum where the results are given in terms of stress, is used. Firstly in order to simplify the fatigue test spectrum, the theoretical cumulative fatigue damage that the metallic parts of the test specimen suffer during the fatigue test is calculated. The theoretical cumulative fatigue damage is calculated according Palmgren Miner rule. The methodology used for the fatigue test spectrum reduction is based on the elimination of the fatigue load cycles that do not contribute for the fatigue damage of the structure. For metallic structure, the truncation was defined in % of GAG, where the load cycles with stress amplitude values below % of GAG do not contribute in the fatigue damage accumulation. When the fatigue test damage (with reduction) reaches a value equal or a little higher to the theoretical fatigue damage (without reduction), the reduction of the fatigue spectrum is concluded and the set of fatigue test load is reached. This reduction include different stress amplitude levels. So, to verify if the test load spectrum can get

similar parameters for different stress level, four reference damages values (0.25, 0.5, 1.0 and 2.0) for four different corresponding stress levels is showed in the figure 6. After this phase, the reduction of cycles based on load cycles with small stress amplitude levels was made for composites structure. The figure 7 give an idea of the purpose. Then, using the Super Mic-Mac+ (SMM+) tool [8] the damage fraction results after 10^6 cycles are quickly obtained as showed in the figure 8. Damage fraction below 1.00, indicated the possibility to reduce the spectrum loading. The figure 9 shows the possibility to combine different load cases. The report of the reference [9] confirmed the expectation about the spectrum reduction.

4 Conclusions

The micro-mechanics theory is coming to complete the theory of failure and durability in terms of the fiber, matrix and interface. The analysis tool proposed by S.W. Tsai and S.K. Ha has the advantages to be simple in the use but supported by a complete and comprehensive theory. The examples showed that is possible minimize the risk in a certification campaign. Other applications of this tool are weight saving and inspection interval reduction.

Fig. 1. Room temperature test condition

Fig. 2. Temperature and humidity controlled

Fig. 3. Truncation's interpretation [3,10]

Fig. 6. First truncation investigated

• SMM RTD & ETW – Static - 24 / 70°C

Fig. 4. ELF Simulation by SMM - 70°C

Fig. 7. Reduced spectrum investigation

• SMM RTD & ETW – Static - 24 / 82°C

Fig. 5. ELF Simulation by SMM - 82°C

OUTPUT	Constituent Failure		Results for each Load #				
	Load_cr		Load #1	Load #2	Load #3	Load #4	Load #5
Critical Load #	k_cr		0.323	0.314	0.289	0.307	0.305
Critical failure index	D_cr	0.005	0.002	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.002
Failure mode	F_mode	fiber	matrix	matrix	matrix	matrix	matrix
Critical ply	Ply_cr	5	15	15	15	15	15
Critical angle	Angle_cr	0	-45	-45	-45	-45	-45

Fig. 8. Damage Fraction Output in the SMM+.

• SMM+ V105

Fig. 9. Types of Loading and Parameters in the SMM+.

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